

**LEVEL OF KNOWLEDGE ON TRANSITIONAL DEVICES IN WRITTEN
COMPOSITIONS AND WRITING DIFFICULTIES OF
GRADE 10 STUDENTS**

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Level of Knowledge on Transitional Devices in Written Compositions and Writing Difficulties of Grade 10 Students

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Abstract

This study aimed to determine the level of knowledge on transitional devices in written compositions and writing difficulties of Grade 10 students in Aleosan Secondary Schools. In employing the descriptive-correlational design, the study determined and described the respondents' demographic profiles, such as sex, age, level of the knowledge of the usage of transitional devices in written compositions, and their writing difficulties. Also, the study determined the significant difference in the level of knowledge on transitional devices in written compositions between male and female Grade 10 students and the significant difference in their writing difficulties. The paragraph test and writing test were the main instruments of this study. Findings revealed no significant difference in the level of knowledge of transitional devices in written composition between male and female respondents. However, there is a significant difference in their writing difficulties. Moreover, there is a significant relationship between the level of knowledge of transitional devices and the writing difficulties encountered by the respondents.

Keywords: *level of knowledge, transitional devices, written compositions, difficulties*

Introduction

Transitional devices support good writing. With skilful use and application of the principles of unity and coherence in sentences and paragraphs, these devices help the writer seamlessly bring his readers from one idea to another, thus making them follow his ideas and thoughts easily (Othman, 2019; Lili, 2021). To write suitable compositions, writers must construct grammatically correct sentences and a unified and coherent text using transitional devices (Darweesh & Kadhim, 2016).

However, studies have shown that some students need help correctly identifying and applying transitional devices in written compositions. Othman (2019) revealed that 52 percent of all errors in written paragraphs were errors in transitional devices. Also, Lili (2021) bared weak, confusing, or illogical organization in Chinese students' writing since they often need to pay more attention to transitional devices in English writing and use them properly or overuse them. More specifically, students misused transitional devices (Hamed, 2014) and the words in the learners' writings in English (Nasser, 2017).

Other writing difficulties still exist despite the grammar conventions taught explicitly in schools. For instance, Filipino students committed syntax-level errors from high school to college (Gustilo & Magno, 2012). Also, several errors were found in Portillo-San Miguel's (2021) study, which revealed that students produced 93 errors in 12 students' writing, including grammar, mechanics, and transitional devices.

In the study of Roxas (2020), he found out about writers' difficulties in comprehending academic writing prompts and organizing and maintaining coherence in their compositions. Similarly, Pablo and Lasaten (2018) uncovered that the predominant challenges of student organization is the need for more connectives. Students failed to connect one idea or provide a shift from one idea to another using transitional devices.

In the local context, based on the experiences and observations of the researcher and the English teachers, the writing compositions of junior high school students showed various problems in content, structures used, and organization of ideas. Students write essays with only a few sentences to almost none or compositions that lack connectors or transitional devices. Despite explicit instruction on the rudiments of composition writing, students still needed help to produce excellent and effective essays.

Hence, the researcher conducted this study to determine the level of knowledge on transitional devices and the writing difficulties of Grade 10 students of the secondary cluster of Aleosan.

Research Questions

This study aimed to determine the level of knowledge on transitional devices and writing difficulties among Grade 10 students in Aleosan Secondary Schools. Specifically, it attempted to answer the following questions:

1. What is the respondents' demographic profile regarding age and sex?
2. What is the respondents' level of knowledge on the usage of transitional devices in written compositions?
3. What do the respondents encounter in writing difficulties in written compositions, subject-verb agreement, pronoun usage, transitional devices, spelling, and punctuation?
4. Is there a significant difference in the level of knowledge on transitional devices in written compositions between male and female Grade 10 students?
5. Is there a significant difference in the writing difficulties between male and female respondents?

6. Is there a significant relationship between the level of knowledge on transitional devices and the writing difficulties encountered by Grade 10 students?

Literature Review

Transitional Devices

Transitional devices lead readers to make sure of connection or assumption. A few lead readers forward and imply the building of an idea, while others make readers compare ideas or draw conclusions from the preceding ideas. It can be used (by students and teachers alike) to find the correct expression. English transition words are essential since they connect ideas and can introduce a particular shift, contrast or opposition, emphasis or agreement, purpose, result, or conclusion in the line of argument (Weber & Stolley, 2011).

In Lili's (2021) paper, *The Application of Transitional Devices in English Writing Teaching*, he claimed that transitional devices show the relationship between sentences or paragraphs of a text or sections of a speech. Transitional words, the logical link of the text structure, strengthen the article's logical relationship. Moreover, they make the structure more rigorous and coherent.

Transitional devices can include those that indicate agreement, addition, or similarity, such as additionally, in like manner, similarly, also, along with, and; those that demonstrate an example, show support, or emphasize, such as namely, notably, to clarify, for instance, for example; to indicate an effect, result, or consequence such as because, consequently, thus, hence; to indicate contradiction, opposition, or limitation which includes in contrast, on the other hand, conversely (Possel, 2013).

In the book published and revised (September 12, 2022) by Jack Caulfield entitled *Transition Words & Phrases | List & Examples*, there are four main types of transition words: additive, adversative, causal, and sequential.

Within each category, words are divided into several more specific functions.

Additive Transition Words

Additive transition words introduce new information or examples. They can expand, compare with, or clarify the preceding text.

Addition

Transition words and phrases: indeed, furthermore, moreover, additionally, and, also, both x and y, not only x but also y, besides x, in fact

Introduction

Example sentence: Several researchers have previously explored this topic. For instance, Smith (2014) examined the effects of...

Transition words and phrases: such as, like, notably, including, as an illustration, for example, for instance, in particular, to illustrate, especially, notably

Reference

Transition words and phrases: considering x, regarding x, regarding x, as for x, concerning x, the fact that x, on the subject of x

Similarity

Example sentence: It was impossible to establish a correlation between these variables. Similarly, the connection between x and y remains unclear...

Transition words and phrases: similarly, in the same way, by the same token, in like manner, equally, likewise

Clarification

Transition words and phrases: that is (to say), namely, specifically, more precisely, in other words

Adversative Transition Words

They can introduce information that disagrees or contrasts with the preceding text.

Conflict

Example sentence: The novel does deal with the theme of family. However, its central theme is more broadly political...

Transition words and phrases: but, although, though, equally, by way of contrast, while, on the other hand, (and) yet, whereas, in contrast, (when) in fact, conversely, whereas

Concession

Transition words and phrases: even so, nonetheless, nevertheless, even though, on the other hand, admittedly, despite x, notwithstanding x,(and) still, although, in spite of x, regardless (of x), (and) yet, though, granted x

Replacement

Example sentence: The character of Godfrey is often viewed as selfish or at least self-absorbed.

Transition words and phrases: (or) at least, (or) rather, instead, or (perhaps) even, if not

Causal Transition Words

Causal transition words describe cause and effect.

Condition

Example sentence: We qualified survey responses as positive only if the participant selected "agree" or "strongly agree." Otherwise, the results were recorded as negative.

Transition words and phrases: (even/only) if/when, on (the) condition that, in the case that, granted (that), provided/providing that, in case, in the event that, as/so long as, unless, given that, being that, inasmuch/insofar as, in that case, in (all) other cases, if so/not, otherwise

Purpose

Example sentence: We used accurate recording equipment so that our results would be as precise as possible.

Transition words and phrases: to, in order to/that, for the purpose of, in the hope that, so that, to the end that, lest, with this in mind, so as to, so that, to ensure (that)

Sequential Transition Words

Enumeration

Example sentence: This has historically had several consequences. First, the conflict should be given the weight of other conflicts in historical narratives. Second, its causes are inadequately understood. Third,...

Transition words and phrases: first, second, third...

Initiation

Transition words and phrases: in the first place, initially, first of all, to begin with, at first

Continuation

Example sentence: Subsequently, I discuss the way in which the country's various ethnic minorities were affected by the conflict.

Transition words and phrases: subsequently, previously, eventually, next, before x, afterwards, after x, then

Conclusion

Example sentence: Finally, I consider these two themes in combination.

Transition words and phrases: to conclude (with), as a final point, eventually, at last, last but not least, finally, lastly

Resumption

Example sentence: To return to my main argument, it is clear that...

Transition words and phrases: to return/returning to x, to resume, at any rate

Summation

Example sentence: Patel (2015) comes to a similar conclusion. In summary, the four studies considered here suggest a consensus that the solution is effective.

Transition words and phrases: as previously stated/mentioned, in summary, as I have argued, overall, as has been mentioned, to summarize, briefly, given these points, in view of x, as has been noted, in conclusion, in sum, altogether, in short

Writing Difficulties/Problems

On subject-verb agreement, students commit errors in writing their compositions. The literature reviewed in this section presents these errors. In their study on Errors in Subject-Verb Agreement: A Study Based on Bangladeshi University Students, Sufian and Harun (2018) analyzed the common errors regarding the agreement between the subject and verb in the writings of the EFL (English as a Foreign Language) 1 learners at the tertiary level. The researchers followed the qualitative method. The data was collected from the write-ups of 50 students at the tertiary level from a renowned private university in Bangladesh. In addition, the researcher interviewed five teachers and scholars to collect some data for the research and triangulate it. The researchers analyzed the three most common

errors regarding Subject-Verb Agreement (SVA) students make while writing a paragraph through an error analysis process. The researchers observed that most students need help with using subjects that are supposed to agree with the verbs, especially in using third-person singular and plural numbers in their sentences.

Similarly, in their study of the Knowledge on Subject-Verb Agreement of Grade 7 Students: Basis for Remedial Teaching, Cabaltica and Osabel (2021) states that the knowledge level of English of Grade 7 learners of President Ramon Magsaysay State University in subject-verb agreement is proficient which has the mean of 53.58 and a standard deviation of 7.18. The subject-verb agreement rule known to the respondents is rule number 19: the personal pronoun "I" requires a plural verb. Sixty-five percent of the respondents are female, while thirty-five percent are male. A descriptive survey research design with the conceptual test was used as the main instrument of the study to measure the learners' knowledge of subject-verb agreement.

Some students made an error in Portillo-San Miguel's (2021) study on pronoun usage. She revealed that students produced 93 errors in 12 students' writing: errors in the production of verb group, errors in the agreement between subject and verb, errors in the use of an article, errors in the use of prepositions, errors in pluralization, errors in the use of the pronoun, and errors in the use of a conjunction. Furthermore, some participants needed help introducing topics and developing paragraphs during the writing task.

In his study of using conjunctions in argumentative essays, Hamed (2014) found that the students misused conjunctions. The findings showed that the students encountered most problems using adversative conjunctions, followed by additive and casual ones.

Problems with the use of conjunctions also surfaced in Alawdi's (2015) study entitled *The Use of Cohesive Devices by EFL (English as a Foreign Language) Learners of English at Saber Faculty of Education*. It analyzed the students' samples of responses to the writing task given to them. Regarding the students' performance of grammatical transition, the results showed that the students used conjunctions more than reference ties. In contrast, there was no indication of the use of ellipsis and substitution. In terms of erroneousness, the study revealed that there were more correct forms of reference and conjunctions than erroneous ones. In comparing the incorrect forms of the two categories, the findings indicated that conjunctions accounted for more errors than reference ties.

For instance, Oroji and Ghane (2014) investigated the use of transitional devices in English Book 3 of Iranian High School. They found that reference ties were the most frequently used in the book, followed by conjunctions, lexical cohesion, substitution, and ellipsis.

In Gepila's (2018) conference paper on the composition writing competency of Grade 7 students entitled "The Impregnable Composition Writing Competency and Teaching Writing Methodologies" at the 4th International Research Conference on Higher Education, he detailed the problems or lapses in organization and content, among others, of his respondents. In his paper, some compositions could be more robust regarding his respondents' use of cohesive/ transitional devices, to have points that were not related to each other or unclear, and to have problematic or missing conclusions. Therefore, some compositions could have been more structured with more robust or transitional devices and unclear and unrelated points or details. For content, the three informants shared that some compositions need help providing relevant reasons, examples, and substantiation. Thus, the composition's content needs to be improved.

Similarly, a study conducted by Nasser (2017) entitled *A study of errors in the use of grammatical cohesive devices in argumentative texts written by Yemeni EFL (English as a Foreign Language) learners*, published in the *International Journal of Applied Research* investigated errors in the use of grammatical transitional devices in argumentative texts written by EFL (English as a Foreign Language) learners in the Yemeni context. Nasser (2017) collected data by asking the learners to write an argumentative essay on given topics, and data analysis revealed that the students needed help with grammatical transitional devices. Because of such difficulties, students make errors in producing transitional argumentative texts. Deviations in using reference ties, substitutions, ellipses, and conjunctions represented these errors. They are omitting, overusing, or misusing the cohesive devices. Also, the study's results revealed that the most frequent category of such errors was tagged as reference errors, followed by erroneous conjunctions, substitutions, and ellipses, respectively. However, the lowest percentage of errors in substituting ellipses does not mean that the students need help using such categories.

A look into other studies on transitional devices reveals problems. In their research on *Cohesive Errors in Writing among ESL (English as a Second Language) Pre-Service Teachers*, Kwan and Yunus (2014) they were focused on transition errors in writing among pre-service teachers of medium and high proficiency levels as measured by a Malaysian University English Test. In the analysis of the participants' essays, they found that both groups, teachers of a high proficiency level and teachers of a medium proficiency level, encountered collocation problems as the most challenging issues. The results of the other categories of transition showed that the participants with medium proficiency levels made the most frequent errors in lexical cohesion, reference, and conjunction, respectively. In contrast, those with high proficiency levels committed more errors in lexical cohesion, ellipsis, and reference, respectively. Moreover, the findings revealed that ellipses accounted for more errors in the writings of the highly proficient teachers than the medium proficient ones.

Guna and Ngadiman (2015) analyzed thirty-nine students' essays to investigate the transitional devices used in the cause-effect essays. Their study, *The Cohesive Devices Used in the Cause-Effect Essay Written by the English Department Students*, pointed out that the students used transitional devices represented by reference, substitution, conjunction, and lexical cohesion in their writings. Regarding the erroneous use of transitional devices, the results revealed the most frequent errors using reference ties, followed by lexical cohesion,

conjunction, and substitution.

Aldera (2016) investigated the transition in the written discourse of students of Arab English as a Foreign Language. He conducted his study, *Cohesion in Written Discourse: A Case Study of Arab EFL (English as a Foreign Language) Students*, which involved eight English students at the Department of English, Najran University, Kingdom of Saudi Arabia. In his study, he found errors in using transitional devices, among other errors the students committed in their written discourse. The results showed that the highest percentage of errors in the use of transitional devices was in the use of reference, followed by errors in ellipsis.

In the study of Dirmayani (2019) entitled *Analyzing Transitional Devices in Essay Writing*, the students used transitional words to indicate connection or addition, especially of items within the same type, to explain the why in a situation, for was used; to suggest an option or alternative, or was used just once correctly, but was not misused; to show a contrast, yet and but were used once incorrectly. Moreover, there was no clause connector about the two similar items used. To show a cause and effect, because, so, and as were used correctly by the students in their essays. To show a relationship between two clauses involving a transition of time or place, where, which, and when were used. No clause connector to show chronological order, such as before and after. He concluded that students have good scores in transitional devices, and the student's ability to use transitional devices in making a sentence was reasonable. The connectors used by students were, but not yet, or, for, if, so, because, where, which, when, and that.

In the study *Common Writing Problems and Writing Attitudes among Freshman University Students in Online Learning Environments: An Exploratory Study*, Ramos and Gatcho (2020) found that most of the surface problems manifested in their written outputs were related to verbs, followed by those related to nouns and prepositions and on the other hand, adjectives, adverbs, and interjections accounted for the least number of surface errors. Regarding verbs, the observed trend among the many participants of the study was that most of them committed errors in verb tenses, particularly inconsistencies. They further indicated that most participants always loved writing about topics they were familiar with and those that interested them. In terms of writing about familiar topics, one of the possible reasons behind the results could be that the participants' exposure to written information and the English language on the internet and print may have increased their confidence in reading and writing about contemporary topics (example fashion, technology, and current events) since they now study in the conveniences of their homes. Based on the interview with the participants, most stated that they often reflect on their performance during the writing process, possibly due to the student's self-awareness of their overall performance in every writing task, especially regarding grammar, mechanics, and content.

In *Exploration on Senior High School Students Academic Writing Difficulties*, Roxas (2020) found out that the results expound on the different Academic Writing difficulties encountered by the participants in terms of the task environment, writers' long-term memory, and writing process. He revealed that due to limited vocabulary, the participants experienced difficulties in comprehending academic writing prompts and in finding teachers' instructions and prompts unclear, which may have something to do with students' level of mastery in English as most of the student's first language is Filipino or a different dialect, and in formulating a topic.

The same struggle students experience when asked to write by Santos (2018). In their study, *Overcoming Writing Apprehension Through Photovoice: Basis for Interdisciplinary Approach in Teaching Creative Nonfiction*, they revealed that students struggled in choosing topics, crafting a good beginning paragraph, and paragraph development when given a writing activity.

A study by Adas and Bakir (2013) on *Writing Difficulties and New Solutions: Blended Learning as an Approach to Improve Writing Abilities* claimed that students in the Arab world have experienced writing difficulties in English. However, through the blended learning approach and innovative modes of assessment, instructors were able to (a) develop students' understanding and use of some related points and writing mechanisms, (b) emphasize group effectiveness skills using technology, (c) emphasize communication skills that encouraged students to share ideas and opinions, and, (d) facilitate learning the foreign language quickly in informal settings among the students in their free time.

Meanwhile, the study by Widianingsih and Gulö (2016) titled *Grammatical Difficulties Encountered by Second Language Students* showed that the students' significant errors were related to plural markers, articles, verbs, and tenses. Additionally, it was mentioned in Chou's study (2011) that L1 interference, the lack of ideas, and unclear instructions for the task given to learners are some of the causes of difficulty in writing.

In a study related to spelling and punctuation by Abderraouf (2016) on *Investigating EFL (English as a Foreign Language) Students' Writing Difficulties and Common Errors in Writing*, the researcher concluded that improving students' writing skills is a challenging task, especially in the case of foreign learners. Writing as a cognitive process requires profound consideration of the rules and careful use of the target language. Students generally hesitate to write while writing composition, for they strive to find the right words, struggle with the language's grammar, or find the punctuation difficult. Most errors were spelling, capitalization, punctuation, and vocabulary (word choice).

In the study of Alsamdani (2010) on *The Relationship Between Saudi EFL (English as a Foreign Language) Students' Writing Competence, L1 (First Language) Writing Proficiency, and Self-regulation to have free-error writing*, learners should carefully consider how to form a thesis statement, write convincing supporting sentences, and finally edit them, meanwhile, in the study of Dallagi (2020) on *Writing Strategies Across Four Disciplines in a Tunisian Context* that students needed to be made aware of some strategies which highlighted the significance of explicit instruction from their teachers. Also, students must reflect on and evaluate their performance

and writing strategies.

Mohamed and Zouaoui's (2014) journal entitled *EFL Writing Hindrances and Challenges: The Case of Second-Year Students of English at Djillali Liabes* found the results that the second-year learners from the English Department of Djillali Liabes University encountered difficulties related to vocabularies like spelling, word choice, and wrong words. Learners could not spell the words, know their meaning, or identify their sound representations and use a minimal number of corresponding English words and expressions. Mohamed and Zouaoui (2014) revealed that learners experienced these difficulties because of a lack of motivation, interest, and reading practice.

In the study by Gustilo (2016) on *Differences in Less Proficient and More Proficient ESL (English as a Second Language) College Writing in the Philippine Setting*, the resource variables identified were content knowledge, linguistic knowledge, writing approach, and writing experience. The researcher affirmed that good or more proficient writers hold extensive vocabulary and topic knowledge. According to her, the lack of topic familiarity and insufficient vocabulary may have constrained the less proficient writers and made it difficult for them to construct quality texts. Abundant evidence also attested to the centrality of linguistic knowledge in developing writing skills. Linguistic knowledge involves mastery of spelling, grammar, genre conventions, and other linguistic aspects. In her study, only vocabulary significantly differs in the mean scores of the three linguistic knowledge measures. She implies that both good and bad writers under study were not constrained by spelling and grammar issues—a finding which is a logical one since the students who were recruited in the present study are college students and the length of their language instruction in Philippine schools has already given them considerable mastery of spelling and grammar of the English language.

Riazi (2014) examined the impact of teaching transitional words on the writing performance of male and female grade 10 students in Iran. She found that teaching transitional words affected the students' writing performance and that female students improved more than male students.

Robertson, Taczak, and Yancey (2012) stated the accuracy and effectiveness of students' utilization of transitional devices in their written compositions to their pre-existing knowledge or level of knowledge.

In summary, the literature and studies included emphasized the students' level of knowledge in using transitional devices and the students' writing difficulties encountered in different types of essays, such as narrative and argumentative. Prevalent among the errors was the use of the connectors labelled as misuse or overuse of the language structures in the sentences, including problems or lapses in organization and content and weak or limited transitional devices in different modes of writing. Some literature and studies also revealed grammar, mechanics, and spelling errors. Several reasons explain the erroneous use of transitional devices and errors the students committed in writing. Common among them were the prior knowledge and experiences of the students about writing and using transitional devices correctly or appropriately.

This study focused on the level of knowledge of Grade 10 students on their use of transitional devices in writing essays about a given topic. It also looked into the students' writing difficulties in subject-verb agreement, pronoun usage, and use of transitional devices, spelling, and punctuation marks when writing an article asked by their language teachers in their class. Also, the researcher conducted the study during the COVID-19 pandemic, in which the learning mode was modular.

Methodology

Research Design

The study employed a descriptive-correlational research design. It was descriptive because it determined or described the respondents' profiles, such as sex, age, writing difficulties, and level of knowledge of transitional devices in written compositions. It was correlational since it determined the significant difference in the level of knowledge on transitional devices in written compositions and writing difficulties between male and female Grade 10 students and the significant relationship between the level of knowledge on transitional devices and writing difficulties encountered by the Grade 10 students.

Respondents

The researcher conducted this study in three public junior high schools in Aleosan, Cotabato. The respondents comprised 114 Grade 10 students.

Instruments

In this study, the researcher employed a test as the main instrument to gather the data. For the paragraph test, the students carefully read the paragraph about "My Word for 2012: Community" and underlined the correct transitional device in the parentheses to complete the sentence best. The respondents will write essays based on the given writing test topics. The respondents had 1 hour to write their essays on the subject of their choice. Thus, the learners were required to write at least 200 words on one of the following topics: (a) The Person I Admire the Most, (b) The Challenges You Have Encountered During the Pandemic, or (c) Reasons for Engaging in Social Media. The tests have bases for determining the ability of the students to use transitional devices appropriately and the difficulties encountered in written compositions in terms of subject-verb agreement, pronoun usage, transitional devices, spelling, and punctuation.

Procedure

Before the study, the researcher acquired permission to conduct the study through a letter from the Dean of the Graduate School of Notre Dame of Midsayap College. After completing the needed documents, the researcher sought permission from the Office of the Schools Division Superintendent to conduct the study and administer the questionnaire. Upon approval, the researcher sent a letter of authorization to the principal of the concerned schools. The respective class advisers of the study respondents were informed, too. The researcher asked for the names of all the Grade 10 students. The researcher gave a letter of permission to conduct the study and administer the composition writing and paragraph tests to the respondents' advisers. The researcher made the schedule for the test.

During the study, students strictly followed the health protocols in writing tests. The respondents were seated at least 1 meter apart from one another.

Before the test, the researcher oriented the respondents about the procedure. The respondents are 114 Grade 10 students from the three junior high schools in Aleosan. In one hour, they finished answering the paragraph and wrote an essay with at least 200 words on one of the topics familiar to them. They used English as the medium in writing the composition. The data were collected using a free composition writing and paragraph test.

Results and Discussion

This section presents the results of the study. The researcher presented the data in a tabular form, which includes the profile of the respondents, their level of knowledge on the usage of transitional devices in written compositions, and the writing difficulties encountered by the respondents in their writing compositions in terms of subject-verb agreement, antecedent, transitional devices, spelling, and punctuations.

Demographic Profile of the Respondents

Table 1 shows the profile of the respondents in terms of age and sex. Based on the findings, more than half of the respondents, or 66 who were involved in the study, are 16. It means most of those whose written compositions are regular Grade 10 students. There were 24 respondents aged 17 years old and 20 respondents aged 15 years old who were also part of the study. Moreover, respondents aged 19 and 24 yielded the same lowest frequency of 1 or 0.90 percent. It means that over aged students became the respondents to the study.

The table further reveals that more than half of the respondents are female, with 67.50 percent of the 114 respondents, and only 32.50 percent are male.

Table 1. *Profile of Respondents*

<i>Variable</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
Age		
15	20	17.50
16	66	57.90
17	24	21.10
18	2	1.80
19	1	0.90
24	1	0.90
Total Mean Age of 16-20 years old	114	100.00
Sex		
Female	37	32.50
Male	77	67.50
Total	114	100.00

Level of Knowledge on the Usage of Transitional Devices in Written Compositions

The level of knowledge on the usage of transitional devices in written compositions is presented in Table 2.

Table 2. *Level of Knowledge on the Usage of Transitional Devices in Written Compositions*

<i>Traditional Devices</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>	<i>Description</i>
Use of Traditional Devices			
1-4 Errors in the Use of Transitional Devices	1	0.90	Good
5-8 Errors in the Use of Transitional Devices	22	19.30	Satisfactory
9 or More Errors in the Use of Transitional Devices	91	79.80	Needs Improvement
Total	114	100.00	
Maximum Score 17		Maximum Error 18	
Minimum Score 6		Minimum Error 5	

The table reveals that only one respondent, or 0.90 percent of the 114 respondents, was found to have a Good level of knowledge after having incurred only 1-4 errors in the use of transitional devices in his written composition. Meanwhile, 22 respondents were described as Satisfactory with their level of use of transitional devices. However, most 91 respondents Needed Improvement in their use of

transitional devices in their written compositions.

Writing Difficulties Encountered by the Respondents in Written Compositions in Terms of Subject-Verb Agreement, Pronoun Usage, Use of Transitional Devices, Spelling, and Punctuation Marks

Table 3 presents the writing difficulties encountered by the respondents in written compositions in terms of subject-verb agreement, pronoun usage, use of transitional devices, spelling, and punctuation marks.

Table 3. *Writing Difficulties Encountered by the Respondents in Written Compositions in Terms of Subject-Verb Agreement, Pronoun Usage, Use of Transitional Devices, Spelling, and Punctuation Marks*

Areas for Writing Difficulties	Inter-Raters' Assessment								Description
	First Rater		Second Rater		Third Rater		Total		
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	
1. Subject-Verb Agreement	2.81	0.82	2.77	0.82	2.78	0.86	2.79	0.83	Satisfactory
2. Pronoun Usage	2.92	0.84	2.89	0.84	3.05	0.90	2.95	0.86	Satisfactory
3. Use of Transitional Devices	2.59	0.84	2.55	0.84	2.84	0.92	2.66	0.87	Needs Improvement
4. Spelling	3.83	1.12	3.72	1.13	3.46	1.08	3.67	1.11	Good
5. Punctuation Marks	2.43	0.65	2.40	0.63	2.64	0.85	2.49	0.71	Needs Improvement
Overall Mean	2.92		2.87		2.95				Satisfactory
Overall SD		0.85		0.85		0.92			
Grand Mean	2.91								Satisfactory
Average SD	0.87								

Scale	Range	Description	Interpretation (1)
5	4.25-5.00	Excellent	All verbs are consistent with their subjects
4	3.49-4.24	Good	1-3 verbs show inconsistency with their subjects
3	2.74-3.48	Satisfactory	4-6 verbs show inconsistency with their subjects
2	2.00-2.73	Needs Improvement	7 or more verbs show inconsistency with their subjects
Interpretation (2)			
5	4.25-5.00	Excellent	All pronouns agree w/ their antecedents in person & in number
4	3.49-4.24	Good	1-3 pronouns don't agree w/ their antecedents in person & in number
3	2.74-3.48	Satisfactory	4-6 pronouns don't agree w/ their antecedents in person & in number
2	2.00-2.73	Needs Improvement	7 or more pronouns don't agree w/ their antecedents in person & in no.
Interpretation (3)			
5	4.25-5.00	Excellent	No error in the use of transitional devices
4	3.49-4.24	Good	1-2 errors in the use of transitional devices
3	2.74-3.48	Satisfactory	3-4 errors in the use of transitional devices
2	2.00-2.73	Needs Improvement	5 or more errors in the use of transitional devices
Interpretation (4)			
5	4.25-5.00	Excellent	All words in the sentence are correctly spelled
4	3.49-4.24	Good	1 or 2 words in the sentence are spelled incorrectly
3	2.74-3.48	Satisfactory	3 or 4 words in the sentence are spelled incorrectly
2	2.00-2.73	Needs Improvement	More than 4 words in the sentence are misspelled
Interpretation (5)			
5	4.25-5.00	Excellent	All sentences are punctuated w/ correct internal & end punctuation marks
4	3.49-4.24	Good	A few sentences are punctuated w/ correct internal & end punctuation marks
3	2.74-3.48	Satisfactory	Some sentences have incorrect or missing internal & end punctuation marks
2	2.00-2.73	Needs Improvement	Many sentences have incorrect or missing internal & end punctuation marks

The table reveals that the respondents' usage of verbs was inconsistent with their subjects, making them Satisfactory in terms of Subject-Verb Agreement with a total mean of 2.79.

Moreover, as reflected in Table 3, the respondents' usage of pronouns was inconsistent with their antecedents in person and number, making them Satisfactory in terms of Pronoun Usage with a total mean of 2.95.

The table also shows that the respondents Need Improvement after they earned the total mean of 2.66 with a total standard deviation of 0.87 regarding their use of transitional devices in their written compositions. They misused five or more transitional devices in their compositions, making some ideas not seamlessly connected.

Regarding spelling, the respondents incurred only 1-2 misspelled words in their sentences. Hence, they rated themselves as Good after earning a mean of 3.67 with a standard deviation of 1.11.

Regarding their skill in using punctuation marks in their written compositions, the respondents needed to correct their internal and end punctuation marks in many of their sentences. As shown in the table, the respondents Need Improvement in their use of punctuation marks after they earned a total mean of 2.49 with a standard deviation of 0.71.

The respondents demonstrated a Satisfactory performance overall, achieving mean ratings of 2.92, 2.87, and 2.95, respectively, as assessed by the raters. The standard deviations associated with these ratings were 0.85, 0.85, and 0.92, respectively. Notably, their proficiency in the use of Subject-Verb and Pronoun-Antecedent was Satisfactory. Additionally, they exhibited Good spelling skills, but there is room for Improvement in their use of transitional devices and punctuation marks. Regarding agreement rules, their collective performance yielded a grand mean of 2.91, with a standard deviation of 0.87.

Difference in the Level of Knowledge on Transitional Devices in Written Composition between Male and Female Grade 10 Students

Table 4 presents the difference in the level of knowledge on transitional devices in written composition between male and female Grade 10 students.

Table 4. *Difference in the Level of Knowledge on Transitional Devices in Written Composition between Male and Female Grade 10 Students*

Variable		Knowledge on Transitional Devices				
Gender	n	Mean Rank	Z Value	P Value	Interpretation	Decision
Male	37	56.49	-0.23	0.82	Not Significant	Not Rejected
Female	77	57.99				
Total	114					

The table reveals that the null hypothesis states that there is no significant difference in the level of knowledge on transitional devices in written compositions between male and female Grade 10 students, which is not rejected since the p-value of 0.82 is greater than the 0.05 significance level.

Difference in the Writing Difficulties between Male and Female Grade 10 Students

Table 5 shows the difference in the writing difficulties between male and female Grade 10 students.

Table 5. *Difference in the Writing Difficulties between Male and Female Grade 10 Students*

Variable		Writing Difficulties				
Gender	n	Mean Rank	Z Value	P Value	Interpretation	Decision
Male	37	46.12	-2.55	0.011	Significant	Rejected
Female	77	62.97				
Total	114					

The table reveals that the null hypothesis stating a significant difference in the writing difficulties between male and female respondents is rejected since the p-value of 0.011 is lower than the 0.05 significance level.

Relationship between the Level of Knowledge on Transitional Devices and the Writing Difficulties Encountered by Grade 10 Students

Table 6 presents the relationship between the level of knowledge on transitional devices and the writing difficulties encountered by Grade 10 students.

Table 6. *Relationship between the Level of Knowledge on Transitional Devices and the Writing Difficulties Encountered by Grade 10 Students*

Variable		Knowledge on Transitional Devices			
	n	r Value	P Value	Interpretation	Decision
Total	114	0.22*	0.018	Significant	Rejected

Based on the null hypothesis stating that there is no significant relationship between the level of knowledge on transitional devices and the writing difficulties encountered by Grade 10 students the table reveals that it is rejected since the probability value of 0.018 is less than the 2-tailed at 0.05 level of correlation. The r value of 0.22 means that there is a relationship between the level of knowledge on transitional devices and the writing difficulties encountered by Grade 10 students. The higher the level of knowledge on transitional devices, the lesser the writing difficulties among Grade 10 students.

Conclusion

Based on the study's findings, the Grade 10 students must improve their use of transitional devices in their written compositions. Overall, they were good at Spelling since they had only 1 or 2 misspelled words in the sentence. In addition, they were satisfactory on subject-verb agreement and pronoun usage since 4-6 verbs showed inconsistency with their subjects, and 4-6 pronouns did not agree with their antecedents in person and number, respectively. Further, they need to improve on transitional devices and punctuation marks since there were five or more errors in the use of transitional devices, and many sentences need to be corrected or added internal and end punctuation marks. There is no significant difference in the level of knowledge on transitional devices in written compositions between male and female Grade 10 students. However, there is a significant difference in the writing difficulties between male and female respondents. Lastly, the researcher found that Grade 10 students are significantly related to their level of knowledge of

transitional devices and their writing difficulties.

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